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Research Article

Ethnomedicinal plants and traditional healing practices among Tribal groups of Telangana, India: Diversity, Uses and Conservation Imperatives

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ABSTRACT

Traditional botanical knowledge (TBK) related to the use of medicinal plants plays an important role in the primary healthcare system of tribal and rural communities. However, rapid socio-economic changes and environmental degradation are leading to the gradual loss of this valuable indigenous knowledge. The present study aims to document the ethnomedicinal plants used by tribal communities of Telangana, India, and to highlight the importance of conserving these valuable biological resources. Field surveys were conducted in selected tribal areas through interviews with traditional healers, elderly villagers, and knowledgeable informants using semi-structured questionnaires and group discussions. The study revealed about 280 plant species belonging to 89 families and 235 genera are traditionally used for the treatment of various ailments such as fever, skin diseases, digestive disorders, respiratory problems, and wounds. Of these, herbs were predominated with 106 species, followed by trees (83 spp.), climbers (57 spp.) and shrubs (34 spp.). Leaves were found to be the most frequently utilized plant part, followed by roots, bark, and fruits. The results also indicate that unsustainable harvesting, habitat destruction, invasive species, and forest fires pose serious threats to the availability of medicinal plants in the region. Documentation of this traditional knowledge is essential for preserving indigenous healthcare practices and for promoting further pharmacological research. The study highlights the need for sustainable utilization and conservation strategies to protect medicinal plant diversity and associated traditional knowledge systems.

1. Introduction

Indigenous communities living in forested regions possess extensive knowledge about the utilization of plants for food, medicine, and other daily needs. This knowledge, which has been developed through long-term interaction with natural ecosystems, is generally transmitted orally from one generation to another. However, modernization, habitat loss, and socio-cultural changes are gradually eroding these traditional knowledge systems. Consequently, systematic documentation of ethnobotanical information has become increasingly important. Traditional knowledge has also gained recognition as a valuable resource for modern scientific research, particularly in the discovery of new pharmaceutical compounds and bioactive substances. In recent years, ethnobotanical research has attracted considerable attention

due to its potential role in biodiversity conservation, sustainable resource management, and the improvement of rural healthcare systems.

Ethnobotanical investigations have led to the documentation of a large number of wild plants used by the indigenous people to meet their multifarious needs. According to the All India Ethnobiological Survey conducted by the Ministry of Environment and Forests, Government of India, local communities across the country utilize more than 8,000 plant species for various purposes. Among these, nearly 1,800 species are used in Ayurveda, about 600 species in Siddha medicine, and approximately 400 species each in Unani and Homeopathy systems of treatment. The Botanical Survey of India (Howrah) was initiated an official programme in the Economic Botany Section and with this, the ethnobotanical

exploration studies were carried out by Janaki Ammal for the first time in 1954. Consequently, Jain started intensive field exploration studies among tribal areas of central India (Jain, 1963 a-c; 1964 a-c; 1965 a,b).

All these publications have triggered the young minds of botanists, anthropologists and ayurvedic medical practitioners in ethnobotanical activities in early sixties. The All India Coordinated Research Project (AICRP) on Ethnobiology came into operation from 1982 at NBRI, Lucknow, and four centres/circles, namely, Shillong, Howrah, Coimbatore and Port Blair of Botanical Survey of India. Mudgal (1987) documented a synoptic account of ethnobotanical studies carried out in India and Binu et al. (1992) reported the ethnobotanical work carried out in India. Later, Lalramnghinglova and Jha (1999) reviewed the work on ethnobotany of the World with special reference to India. An important prerequisite for proper utilization of raw materials of the country is the survey of its natural resources and the preparation of an inventory. It is necessary to have a full knowledge about the occurrence, abundance, distribution and phenology of various plants for their sustainable utilization. The forests of Telangana have great potential in terms of economic benefits to ethnic people. The Telangana State is one of the timber and non-timber rich forests in the country.

In Telangana, almost certainly for the first time, the ethnobotanical uses of few medicinal plants were recorded in the Forest Flora of Hyderabad (Khan, 1953). Kapoor and Kapoor (1980) listed the wealth of medicinal plants from Karimnagar district. Ramarao (1988) visited Rangapur and Thupakulagudem hamlets and interacted with Koyas and Lambadis of Warangal district for his doctoral work. Ravishankar (1990) and Mamidala et al., (2020) worked on the ethnobotany of Adilabad and Karimnagar districts for his doctoral degree. Ravishanker and Henry (1992) published a brief account of Ethnobotany of Gonds of Adilabad district. Later on, notes on ethnomedicinal uses of some important plant taxa of Mahabubnagar district (Pullaiah and Kumar, 1996; Kumar and Pullaiah, 1998) and folk treatment of bone fracture in Ranga Reddy district (Padmarao and Reddy, 1999) were published. Reddy et al. (1998) recorded the ethnoveterinary plants from Warangal district and of these, 49 plant taxa were included in Dictionary of Ethnoveterinary Plants of India by Jain (1999) as an appendix.

Upadhyay and Chauhan (2000) provided an account of the ethnobotany of Gundala mandal in Khammam district. Reddy and Rao (2002) documented the folklore and ethnomedicinal drugs from Ranga Reddy district. Reddy (2002), Kumar et al., (2017); Poojari et al., (2014) documented ethnobotanical plants for Khammam district. Reddy and Raju (2002) published the ethnobotanical uses by Konda redds of Mothugudem, and Raju and Reddy (2005) enlisted the ethno-botanico-medicinal plants for diarrhoea and dysentery.

A brief report of the ethnoveterinary practices by Koyas in Pakhal wildlife sanctuary by Murthy et al. (2007) whereas Reddy (2008) recorded the medicines from bio-fencing plants from Nalgonda district. Sreeramulu (2008) recorded 313 ethnomedicinal plants from Nalgonda and Warangal districts for his doctoral degree. Reddy et al. (2010) reported 82 medicinal plant species of ethnic use in Medak district. The utilization pattern and diversity of NTFPs from Adilabad district was documented by Omkar et al. (2012). Later, Sreeramulu et al. (2013) reviewed the ethno-botanico-medicine for common human ailments in northern (Warangal) and

southern (Nalgonda) Telangana districts. Suthari et al. (2014a) investigated the traditional knowledge of medicinal plants used by Koya community inhabiting in and around Eturnagaram wildlife sanctuary area and they recorded 237 species of 75 families of Magnoliophyta and four ferns of Pteridophyta as the resources of medicine. Suthari et al. (2014b) enumerated 204 climbing plants of northern Telangana and their ethnomedicinal uses. Saidulu et al. (2015) published the Ethnobotany of Pocharam wildlife sanctuary in the former Medak and Nizamabad districts. Recently, Suthari and Raju (2016) reported the traditional knowledge on 124 flowering plant taxa for poisonous snake-bites used by Koyas of Warangal district whereas Suthari et al. (2016a) documented 470 species of 318 genera and 95 angiosperm families used by Koyas of Warangal North Forest Division of northern Telangana. Mohan et al. (2017a) enlisted 198 ethnomedicinal plants of 165 genera belonging to 72 families whereas Mohan et al. (2017b) recorded 22 antirheumatic plant taxa of 22 genera and 17 families from Kawal wildlife sanctuary of Mancherial district. Suthari et al. (2018) documented the synoptic account on ethnobotanical aspects among the tribal communities in Telangana. Suthari et al. (2021) listed the utility of wild food plants by indigenous tribes from Telangana where Omkar et al. (2022) and Suthari et al. (2023a, b) documented socio-economic empowerment in the rural economy through NTFPs, gum and resin bearing plant taxa and iron deficiency and heredity anaemia in ethnic tribes of Mulugu district of Telangana, respectively.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study area

The present study was conducted in selected forest and tribal-inhabited regions of Telangana State, India. The region lies between latitudes 16°45'-19°55' N and longitudes 77°28'-80°47' E and is characterized by tropical dry deciduous forests. The study area includes tribal settlements located near forest ecosystems where local communities depend heavily on plant resources for healthcare, food, and livelihood. Major tribal groups such as the Koyas and Gonds are largely concentrated in the districts of Bhadradi Kothagudem, Mulugu, and Adilabad, whereas the Chenchus inhabit the forest regions of the Nallamala hills, particularly within the Amrabad and Nagarjunasagar-Srisailem Tiger Reserve areas. The Lambadis (Banjaras) are more widely distributed across agricultural and rural landscapes.

2.2 Data collection

Field surveys were carried out during different seasons to document ethnomedicinal plant species and their traditional uses. Information was collected through direct interaction with local inhabitants, traditional healers, and elderly members of tribal communities who possess extensive knowledge of medicinal plants. Semi-structured interviews, group discussions, and personal observations were employed to gather ethnobotanical information. Data on local plant names, plant parts used, methods of preparation, mode of administration, and ailments treated were carefully recorded. Plant specimens mentioned by informants were collected from their natural habitats during field visits. The collected specimens were identified and updated using www.worldfloraonline.org. The voucher specimens were prepared and preserved for future reference at herbarium of Centre for Floristics & Ethnobotanical Studies (CFES), Vaagdevi Degree & PG College (A), Warangal (acronym: VHW).

2.3 Data analysis

The ethnobotanical data obtained during the study were systematically compiled and analyzed. Medicinal plant species were categorized based on their family, habit, plant parts used, therapeutic applications. The collected information was evaluated to understand the diversity of medicinal plants and their importance in traditional healthcare practices.

The family-wise distribution of plant species recorded in the study area that shows considerable variation in species richness. Among the documented taxa, Fabaceae was the most dominant family with 40 species, contributing significantly to the overall floristic diversity. This was followed by Apocynaceae with 16 species and Malvaceae with 15 species, indicating their notable representation in the vegetation. Euphorbiaceae was represented by 11 species, while Asteraceae accounted for 10 species, showing moderate diversity. In addition to these dominant families, 47 families represented by a single species each. This pattern indicates that while a few families contribute a major share of the species richness, many other families occur with limited representation, reflecting the high taxonomic diversity and heterogeneous nature of the plant community in the study area (Table 1).

Table 2. Life-form composition of the recorded ethnomedicinal plant species from Telangana.

Sl. No.	Habit	No. of Species	%
1	Herbs	106	37.86
2	Trees	83	29.64
3	Climbers	57	20.36
4	Shrubs	34	12.14

Figure-1. Graphical representation of ethnomedicinal plants recorded habit-wise

The analysis of growth forms recorded in the study area reveals noticeable differences in the representation of plant life forms. A total of 280 plant species were documented and categorized into four major habit groups: herbs, trees, climbers, and shrubs. Among these groups, herbs were the most dominant with 106 plant taxa, accounting for the largest share of the total flora. The predominance of herbs associated with their fast growth, short life span, and ability to adapt quickly to seasonal and disturbed environments. Herbaceous plants often occupy open spaces, forest margins, and disturbed habitats, which may explain their higher occurrence in the surveyed area. Trees formed the second largest group with 83 species, indicating a well-represented arboreal component in the vegetation. The

presence of a substantial number of tree species suggests that the area supports a relatively stable ecosystem capable of sustaining perennial woody plants. Trees contribute significantly to ecological balance by providing shade, habitat, and food resources for many organisms while also influencing microclimatic conditions.

Climbers were represented by 57 species, showing moderate diversity within the plant community. Climbers usually depend on trees and shrubs for structural support, and their occurrence reflects the availability of suitable host vegetation. The presence of climbers also enhances structural complexity and species interactions within the ecosystem. In contrast, shrubs were comparatively fewer, with 34 species recorded in the study area. Shrubs generally occupy the intermediate layer of vegetation between herbs and trees. Their relatively lower representation may be influenced by competition with dominant herbaceous species or environmental factors that favor other growth forms (Table 2; Figure 1).

2.4 Conservation Imperatives and Future Prospects

The conservation of medicinal plant resources is essential for maintaining biodiversity as well as sustaining traditional healthcare systems. Increasing pressure on forest ecosystems necessitates the implementation of effective conservation and management strategies to ensure the long-term availability of these valuable plant species.

In-situ Conservation: The establishment of Medicinal Plant Conservation Areas (MPCAs) within forest divisions is crucial. The Amrabad, Pakhal, Eturnagaram and Kawal Tiger Reserves inadvertently serve as in-situ sites for species like *Rauvolfia serpentina*. Establishing protected areas such as wildlife sanctuaries, and community conservation zones helps safeguard natural populations of medicinal plants. Sustainable forest management practices and regulated harvesting can also contribute to maintaining ecological balance and promoting natural regeneration.

Ex-situ Conservation: Initiatives by the Telangana State Medicinal Plants Board (TSMPB) to promote the cultivation of threatened species (like *Ashwagandha*, *Andrographis*, *Aloe*, *Cissus* and *Gymnema*) in farmers' fields can reduce pressure on wild stocks. Botanical gardens, seed banks, tissue culture laboratories, and medicinal plant nurseries play an important role in conserving rare and threatened plant species. Cultivation of medicinal plants in controlled environments can also reduce pressure on wild populations.

Documentation and Intellectual Property: There is an urgent need to digitize the ethnomedicinal knowledge of tribal healers under the People's Biodiversity Registers (PBRs) to prevent biopiracy and ensure benefit-sharing under the Biodiversity Act, 2002.

Sustainable harvesting practices: Adopting non-destructive and scientifically guided harvesting techniques is essential for maintaining plant populations in the wild. Collecting only specific plant parts, harvesting during appropriate seasons, and avoiding uprooting of entire plants can help ensure sustainable utilization of medicinal plant resources.

Community participation: Local and tribal communities play a crucial role in the conservation of forest resources. Encouraging community-based conservation initiatives, awareness

programmes, and participatory forest management can help protect medicinal plants while also supporting the livelihoods of forest-dependent people.

Documentation and knowledge preservation: Systematic documentation of traditional ethnobotanical knowledge is necessary to prevent the loss of valuable indigenous information. Recording traditional medicinal practices and integrating them with scientific research can support the development of new pharmacological products and promote sustainable utilization of plant resources.

Integration with AYUSH: Integrating validated ethnomedicinal practices with the AYUSH system can provide economic incentives to tribal healers and encourage conservation

Research Gap and Objectives of the Present Study

Although several ethnobotanical studies have been conducted in different parts of southern India, systematic documentation of traditional medicinal plant knowledge among many tribal communities of Telangana remains limited. Rapid socio-economic changes, habitat degradation, and declining interest among younger generations threaten the continuity of this indigenous knowledge. Moreover, many medicinal plant species used by tribal healers have not been adequately recorded, scientifically validated, or assessed for their conservation status. Therefore, there is a pressing need to document and preserve ethnomedicinal knowledge before it disappears.

The present study aims to document the traditional knowledge related to medicinal plant use among tribal communities of Telangana. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to: Document the diversity of medicinal plants used by local tribal communities; record traditional methods of preparation and mode of administration of herbal remedies; identify plant species used for the treatment of various human ailments; assess the threats affecting the availability of medicinal plants and highlight the need for conservation strategies. This study is expected to contribute to the preservation of indigenous knowledge, provide baseline information for pharmacological research, and support the sustainable conservation and utilization of medicinal plant resources.

2.5 Threats to the Availability of Medicinal Plants

The availability of medicinal plant resources in forest ecosystems is increasingly threatened by several anthropogenic and ecological factors. These pressures not only reduce the natural populations of valuable plant species but also affect the traditional knowledge systems associated with their use.

Habitat destruction: Rapid conversion of forest areas for agriculture, irrigation projects, infrastructure development, new roads laying and mining has resulted in extensive habitat loss and fragmentation. Such disturbances alter natural ecosystems and significantly reduce the distribution and regeneration potential of many medicinal plant species.

Overexploitation: Several medicinal plants with high commercial demand are harvested unsustainably from the wild. Destructive harvesting methods, such as uprooting entire plants, excessive removal of bark, or collection before seed maturation, adversely affect plant regeneration and lead to the gradual depletion of these species in their natural habitats.

Invasive species: The proliferation of invasive species like *Hyptis suaveolens*, *Lantana camara*, *Chromolaena odorata* and *Parthenium hysterophorus* chokes the growth of native medicinal herbs (Suthari et al., 2016b). These species aggressively colonize degraded and open habitats, outcompeting native vegetation and suppressing the growth of indigenous medicinal plants by monopolizing nutrients, space, and sunlight.

Forest fires: Frequent forest fires, whether natural or human-induced, can severely damage vegetation and reduce the abundance of medicinal plants. Fires not only destroy mature plants but also affect soil fertility, soil pH and texture, seed banks, and the regeneration capacity of many forest species.

Climate change: Changes in temperature, rainfall patterns, and prolonged drought conditions influence plant distribution and phenology. Such climatic variations may affect the growth, flowering, and survival of several medicinal plant species, thereby altering their availability in natural ecosystems.

Loss of traditional knowledge: Traditional ethnomedicinal knowledge is primarily transmitted orally across generations. However, increasing modernization, urban migration, and reduced interest among younger generations are leading to a gradual decline in this indigenous knowledge.

3. Conclusion

The study highlights the rich ethnomedicinal knowledge possessed by tribal groups of Telangana. Telangana represents a significant ethnomedicinal hub in Southern India. The synergy between the state's floral wealth and the indigenous knowledge of its tribal communities offers immense potential for drug discovery and rural healthcare. A considerable diversity of plant species is traditionally used for treating various ailments. However, increasing anthropogenic pressures and intrusion of invasive species threaten the availability of these valuable resources. Therefore, proper documentation, sustainable utilization, and conservation imperatives are essential to preserve both medicinal plant diversity and associated traditional knowledge and the sustainability of this resource is precarious. A balanced approach involving scientific validation, conservation of threatened species, and community participation is essential to preserve the ethnomedicinal heritage of Telangana for future generations.

Competing interests:

The authors declare that they have no competing interests

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Table 1. Common ethnobotanical plants and their ethnic use.

Sl. No.	Scientific Name	Vernacular Name	Family	Parts Useful
1	<i>Abelmoschus esulentus</i> (L.) Moench	Benda	Malvaceae	Seed
2	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L.	Gurije	Fabaceae	Leaf
3	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	Thutturubenda	Malvaceae	Root
4	<i>Acacia caesia</i> (L.) Willd.	Kondakorinda	Fabaceae	Stem bark
5	<i>Acacia chundra</i> (Roxb. ex Rottler) Willd.	Sandra	Fabaceae	Stem bark
6	<i>Acacia leucophloea</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	Tella tumma	Fabaceae	Stem bark
7	<i>Acacia nilotica</i> Delile	Nalla tumma	Fabaceae	Stem bark
8	<i>Acacia sinuata</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Seekakai	Fabaceae	Stem bark
9	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	Muripinda	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
10	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	Uttareni	Amaranthaceae	Root, leaf
11	<i>Acmella paniculata</i> (Wall. ex DC.) R.K.Jansen	Pippallu chettu	Asteraceae	Flower
12	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Correa	Bilva	Rutaceae	Fruit
13	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	Pindi kura	Amaranthaceae	Whole plant
14	<i>Ageratum conyzoides</i> (L.) L.	Gabbu chettu	Asteraceae	Leaf
15	<i>Ageratum houstonianum</i> Mill.	Pokabanthi	Asteraceae	Leaf
16	<i>Ailanthus excelsa</i> Roxb.	Peddamanu	Simaroubaceae	Stem bark
17	<i>Alangium salviifolium</i> (L.f.) Wangerin	Uduga	Alangiaceae	Stem bark
18	<i>Albizia lebeck</i> (L.) Benth.	Dirisena	Fabaceae	Stem bark
19	<i>Albizia odoratissima</i> (L.f.) Benth.	Chinduga	Fabaceae	Stem bark
20	<i>Allium sativum</i> L.	Vellulli	Amaryllidaceae	Bulb
21	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.) Burm.f.	Kalabanda	Xanthorrhoeaceae	Leaf
22	<i>Alstonia scholaris</i> (L.) R.Br.	Edakulapala	Apocynaceae	Stem bark
23	<i>Alternanthera philoxeroides</i> (Mart.) Griseb.	Musli ponnagantikura	Amaranthaceae	Leaf
24	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R.Br. ex DC.	Ponnagantikura	Amaranthaceae	Leaf
25	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	Mullathotakura	Amaranthaceae	Leaf
26	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	Thotakura	Amaranthaceae	Leaf
27	<i>Ammania baccifera</i> L.	Agni vendrapaku	Lythraceae	Leaf
28	<i>Ampelocissus indica</i> (L.) Planch.	Adavi draksha	Vitaceae	Root
29	<i>Anacardium occidentale</i> L.	Jeedi mamidi	Anacardiaceae	Root, stem bark
30	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees	Nelavemu	Acanthaceae	Leaf
31	<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Sims	Dayyam chettu	Lamiaceae	Leaf
32	<i>Annona cherimola</i> L.	Hanumanphal	Annonaceae	Fruit
33	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	Shethalphal	Annonaceae	Leaf, fruit
34	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wall. ex Bedd.	Tiruman	Combretaceae	Gum
35	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	Brahma dandi	Papaveraceae	Latex
36	<i>Argyreia nervosa</i> (Burm.f.) Bojer	Samudrapala	Convolvulaceae	Leaf
37	<i>Aristolochia bracteolata</i> Lam.	Nalleswari	Aristolochiaceae	Root
38	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L.	Gadida gadapa	Aristolochiaceae	Root
39	<i>Artocarpus heterophyllus</i> Lam.	Panasa	Moraceae	Wood
40	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	Satamuli	Asparagaceae	Leaf
41	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss.	Vepa	Meliaceae	Stem bark, leaf
42	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Wettst.	Brahmi	Plantaginaceae	Leaf

43	<i>Balanites roxburghii</i> (L.) Delile	Gare	Balanitaceae	Fruit
44	<i>Baliospermum solanifolium</i> (Burm.) Suresh	Nagadanthi	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
45	<i>Bambusa bambos</i> (L.) Voss	Bongu	Poaceae	Stem (culm), grains
46	<i>Bauhinia vahlii</i> Wight & Arn.	Addaku	Fabaceae	Seed
47	<i>Biophytum sensitivum</i> (L.) DC.	Atti patti	Oxalidaceae	Root, leaf
48	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i> (L.) B.Heyne ex Roth		Acanthaceae	Leaf
49	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	Atikamamidi	Nyctaginaceae	Whole plant
50	<i>Bombax ceiba</i> L.	Buruga	Malvaceae	Stem bark
51	<i>Borassus flabellifer</i> L.	Thaati	Arecaceae	Inflorescence, sap
52	<i>Boswellia serrata</i> Roxb. ex Colebr.	Anduga	Burseraceae	Stem bark
53	<i>Brassica juncea</i> (L.) Czern.	Aavalu	Brassicaceae	Seed
54	<i>Bridelia montana</i> (L.) A.Juss.	Panchotkam	Euphorbiaceae	Root bark
55	<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i> (Lam.) Oken	Ranapala	Crassulaceae	Leaf
56	<i>Caesalpinia bonduc</i> (L.) Roxb.	Gachakaya	Fabaceae	Seed
57	<i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L.) Millsp.	Kandi	Fabaceae	Leaf
58	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) Dryand.	Jilledu	Apocynaceae	Leaf, latex
59	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Aiton) Dryand.	Tella jilledu	Apocynaceae	Leaf
60	<i>Canavalia gladiata</i> (Jacq.) DC.	Adavi chemma	Fabaceae	Leaf
61	<i>Cannabis sativa</i> L.	Ganjai	Cannabinaceae	Leaf
62	<i>Capparis zeylanica</i> L.	Adonda	Capparaceae	Stem bark
63	<i>Capsicum annum</i> L.	Mirapa	Solanaceae	Fruit
64	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	Buddakase chettu	Sapindaceae	Leaf
65	<i>Careya arborea</i> Roxb.	Budadhermi	Lecythidaceae	Stem bark
66	<i>Carica papaya</i> L.	Boppayi	Caricaceae	Fruit
67	<i>Caryota urens</i> L.	Jeeluga	Arecaceae	Leaf, flower
68	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	Rela	Fabaceae	Stem bark
69	<i>Cassine glauca</i> (Rottb.) Kuntze	Bhutankus	Celastraceae	Leaf
70	<i>Cassytha filiformis</i> L.	Paachi teega	Lauraceae	Whole plant
71	<i>Celastrus paniculatus</i> Willd.	Malleru teega	Celastraceae	Stem bark
72	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	Gunugu	Amaranthaceae	Leaf
73	<i>Centella asiatica</i> (L.) Urb.	Saraswati aku	Apiaceae	Leaf
74	<i>Cheilocostus speciosus</i> (J.Koenig) C.D.Specht	Kepu kanda	Costaceae	Leaf
75	<i>Chloroxylon swietenia</i> DC.	Bilugu	Rutaceae	Stem bark
76	<i>Chromolaena odorata</i> (L.) R.M.King & H.Rob.	Kodijuttu chettu	Asteraceae	Leaf
77	<i>Chrysopogon zizanioides</i> (L.) Roberty	Vetiver	Poaceae	Root, leaf
78	<i>Cinnamomum verum</i> J.Presl.	Dalchina chekka	Lauraceae	Stem bark
79	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	Vishaboddi	Menispermaceae	Root, leaf
80	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	Nalleru	Vitaceae	Stem
81	<i>Cleistanthus collinus</i> (Roxb.) Benth. ex Hook.f.	Nalla kodisha	Euphorbiaceae	Stem bark, fruit
82	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	Vaminta	Cleomaceae	Leaf, fruit
83	<i>Clerodendrum phlomidis</i> L.f.	Tekkali	Verbenaceae	Leaf
84	<i>Clitorea ternatea</i> L.	Shankupushpi	Fabaceae	Flower
85	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt	Donda	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit
86	<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> (L.) W.Theob.	Dusara teega	Menispermaceae	Leaf, whole plant
87	<i>Cochlospermum religiosum</i> (L.) Alston	Kondagogu	Cochlospermaceae	Leaf

88	<i>Cocos nucifera</i> L.	Kobbari	Areaceae	Inflorescence
89	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	Ennadri	Commelinaceae	Leaf
90	<i>Crotalaria ramosissima</i> Roxb.	Konda janumu	Fabaceae	Leaf
91	<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i> L.	Giligichakaya	Fabaceae	Root
92	<i>Croton bonplandianum</i> Baill.	Galivana mokka	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
93	<i>Curculigo orchoides</i> Gaertn.	Nelathati	Hypoxidaceae	Tuber
94	<i>Curcuma longa</i> L.	Pasupu	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome
95	<i>Curcuma pseudomontana</i> J. Graham	Adavi pasupu	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome
96	<i>Cuscuta reflexa</i> Roxb.	Pashiteega	Convolvulaceae	Whole plant
97	<i>Cyanthillium cinereum</i> (L.) H.Rob.	Sahadevi	Asteraceae	Leaf
98	<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC.) Stapf	Nimmagaddi	Poaceae	Leaf
99	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	Garika	Poaceae	Leaf
100	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	Thunga	Cyperaceae	Tuber
101	<i>Dalbergia lanceolaria</i> subsp. <i>paniculata</i> (Roxb.) Thoth.	Patchari	Fabaceae	Stem bark
102	<i>Dalbergia latifolia</i> Roxb.	Jitregi	Fabaceae	Stem bark
103	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> DC.	Sissoo	Fabaceae	Stem bark
104	<i>Datura metel</i> L.	Ummetta	Solanaceae	Flower, seed, leaf
105	<i>Delonix elata</i> (L.) Gamble	Chilukepari chettu	Fabaceae	Leaf
106	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.) DC.	Konda saru	Fabaceae	Root
107	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) Wight	Velturu chettu	Fabaceae	Stem bark
108	<i>Dillenia pentagyna</i> Roxb.	Revadi	Dilleniaceae	Stem bark
109	<i>Dioscorea alata</i> L.	Bellam gadda	Dioscoreaceae	Tuber
110	<i>Dioscorea bulbifera</i> L.	Chenna gadda	Dioscoreaceae	Tuber
111	<i>Dioscorea oppositifolia</i> L.	Govinda gadda	Dioscoreaceae	Tuber
112	<i>Dioscorea pentaphylla</i> L.	Pabbu gadda	Dioscoreaceae	Tuber, aerial bulbs
113	<i>Diospyros chloroxylon</i> Roxb.	Illintha	Ebenaceae	Root
114	<i>Diospyros montana</i> Roxb.	Muchi tuniki	Ebenaceae	Stem bark
115	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C.Jeffrey	Putaka kaya	Cucurbitaceae	Leaf
116	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (L.) Jacq.	Devadaru	Sapindaceae	Root
117	<i>Dregea volubilis</i> (L.f.) Benth. ex Hook.f.	Bandigurije	Apocynaceae	Leaf
118	<i>Drimia indica</i> (Roxb.) Jessop	Adavi ulli	Asparagaceae	Bulb
119	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	Guntagalagara	Asteraceae	Leaf
120	<i>Elytraria acaulis</i> (L.f.) Lindau	Edduadugu padam	Acanthaceae	Root
121	<i>Enicostemma axillare</i> (Lam.) A.Raynal.	Resca	Gentianaceae	Whole plant
122	<i>Erythrina variegata</i> L.	Badida	Fabaceae	Leaf
123	<i>Eucalyptus globulus</i> Labill.	Jamail	Myrtaceae	Leaf
124	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i> L.	Jalabhedhi	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
125	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	Reddivari nanubalu	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
126	<i>Euphorbia nivulia</i> Buch.-Ham.	Akujemudu	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
127	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (L.) L.	Vishnukrantham	Convolvulaceae	Leaf
128	<i>Evolvulus nummularius</i> (L.) L.	Akuparni	Convolvulaceae	Leaf
129	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	Marri	Moraceae	Aerial roots
130	<i>Ficus hispida</i> L.f.	Bomma medi	Moraceae	Stem bark, fruit, latex
131	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	Medi	Moraceae	Fruit
132	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	Raavi	Moraceae	Resin

133	<i>Firmiana simplex</i> (L.) W.Wight	Tabasi	Malvaceae	Leaf
134	<i>Flacourtia indica</i> (Burm.f.) Merr.	Nakkaneredu	Salicaceae	Leaf
135	<i>Gardenia latifolia</i> Aiton	Pedda karinga	Rubiaceae	Leaf
136	<i>Getonia floribunda</i> Roxb.	Bontha teega	Combretaceae	Stem exudate, leaf
137	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L.	Naabhi	Colchicaceae	Leaf
138	<i>Grewia hirsuta</i> Vahl	Jibilika	Malvaceae	Flower
139	<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> (Retz.) R.Br. ex Sm.	Podapatri	Apocynaceae	Leaf
140	<i>Habenaria roxburghii</i> Nicolson	Malli sudulu	Orchidaceae	Tuber
141	<i>Haldina cordifolia</i> (Roxb.) Ridsdale	Bandaru	Rubiaceae	Leaf
142	<i>Helicteres isora</i> L.	Nulthada	Malvaceae	Stem bark
143	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R.B. ex Schult.	Sugandhi pala	Apocynaceae	Root
144	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem & Schultes	Yada gaddi	Poaceae	Root
145	<i>Hibiscus rosa-sinensis</i> L.	Mandara	Malvaceae	Leaf, flower
146	<i>Hibiscus surattensis</i> L.	Mullagogu	Malvaceae	Leaf
147	<i>Holarrhena pubescens</i> Wall. ex G.Don	Palakodisa	Apocynaceae	Stem bark
148	<i>Hybanthus enneaspermus</i> (L.) F.Muell.	Ratna purusha, nela kobarri	Violaceae	Whole plant
149	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i> (Schumach.) Heine	Neeti gobbi	Acanthaceae	Leaf
150	<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.) Poit	Mahabeera	Lamiaceae	Leaf
151	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> L.	Neelimandu	Fabaceae	Root, leaf
152	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) K.Gawl.	Gollajiddaku	Convolvulaceae	Root, leaf
153	<i>Ipomoea quamoclit</i> L.	Kasiratnamu	Convolvulaceae	Leaf
154	<i>Ixora arborea</i> Roxb. ex Sm.	Korivi	Rubiaceae	Root
155	<i>Jasminum auriculatum</i> Vahl	Adavi malle	Oleaceae	Leaf
156	<i>Jatropha curcas</i> L.	Adavi amudam	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
157	<i>Justicia procumbens</i> L.	Nagaputta mokka	Acanthaceae	Leaf
158	<i>Lagerstroemia parviflora</i> Roxb.	Chennangi	Lythraceae	Leaf
159	<i>Lannea coromandelica</i> (Houtt.) Merr.	Dumpena	Anacardiaceae	Stem bark
160	<i>Lawsonia inermis</i> L.	Maidaku	Lythraceae	Leaf
161	<i>Leea asiatica</i> (L.) Ridsdale	Neerteega	Leeaceae	Root
162	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> (Retz.) Wight & Arn.	Mukkuthummudu teega	Apocynaceae	Whole plant
163	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link	Thummi	Lamiaceae	Root, leaf
164	<i>Limonia acidissima</i> Groff	Velaga	Rutaceae	Fruit
165	<i>Litsea glutinosa</i> (Lour.) C.B.Rob.	Narra mamidi	Lauraceae	Stem bark
166	<i>Lygodium flexuosum</i> (L.) Sw.	Dayyapu jeda	Lygodiaceae	Leaf
167	<i>Madhuca longifolia</i> var. <i>latifolia</i> (Roxb.) A.Chev.	Ippa	Sapotaceae	Flower
168	<i>Maerua oblongifolia</i> (Forssk.) A.Rich.	Bhuchakra gadda	Capparaceae	Tuber
169	<i>Mangifera indica</i> L.	Mamidi	Anacardiaceae	Seed
170	<i>Maytenus emarginatus</i> (Willd.) Ding Hou	Danthi	Rubiaceae	Leaf
171	<i>Merremia hederacea</i> (Burm.f.) Hallier f.	Thalantu teega	Convolvulaceae	Leaf
172	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	Lajjavathi	Fabaceae	Leaf
173	<i>Mirabilis jalapa</i> L.	Bhadrakshi	Nyctaginaceae	Seed
174	<i>Momordica charantia</i> L.	Kakara	Cucurbitaceae	Leaf
175	<i>Momordica dioica</i> Roxb. ex Willd.	Bodakakara	Cucurbitaceae	Leaf
176	<i>Morinda pubescens</i> Sm.	Togara	Rubiaceae	Fruit
177	<i>Moringa oleifera</i> Lam.	Munuga	Moringaceae	Stem bark, leaf

178	<i>Mucuna pruriens</i> (L.) DC.	Dulagondi	Fabaceae	Fruit
179	<i>Mukia maderaspatana</i> (L.) M.Roem.	Budamadosa	Cucurbitaceae	Root, leaf
180	<i>Murraya koenigii</i> (L.) Spreng.	Karivepa	Rutaceae	Leaf
181	<i>Naringi crenulata</i> (Roxb.) Nicolson	Torri velaga	Rutaceae	Root
182	<i>Nelumbo nucifera</i> Gaertn.	Thamara	Nelumbonaceae	Flower
183	<i>Nerium oleander</i> L.	Ganneru	Apocynaceae	Leaf
184	<i>Nyctanthes arbor-tristis</i> L.	Parijatam	Nyctanthaceae	Leaf
185	<i>Ocimum basilicum</i> L.	Ganapatri	Lamiaceae	Seed
186	<i>Ocimum tenuiflorum</i> L.	Tulasi	Lamiaceae	Leaf
187	<i>Oldenlandia umbellata</i> L.	Chiruveru	Rubiaceae	Whole plant
188	<i>Operculina turpethum</i> (L.) Silva Manso	Tagada	Convolvulaceae	Whole plant
189	<i>Oroxylum indicum</i> (L.) Kurz	Dundilam	Bignoniaceae	Root
190	<i>Osbeckia aspera</i> Bedd.	Thutikara	Melastomataceae	Root
191	<i>Oxalis corniculata</i> L.	Pulichinta	Oxalidaceae	Leaf
192	<i>Oxystelma esculentum</i> (L.f.) Sm.	Dudipala	Apocynaceae	Whole plant
193	<i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	Kourava Pandavula chettu	Passifloraceae	Leaf
194	<i>Pavetta indica</i> L.	Papidi	Rubiaceae	Stem bark
195	<i>Pedaliium murex</i> L.	Peddapalleru	Pedaliaceae	Leaf
196	<i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling.	Adavi chamanthi	Asteraceae	Root
197	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	Dustapu teega	Apocynaceae	Leaf
198	<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	Bokkena	Verbenaceae	Leaf
199	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schumach. & Thonn.	Nela usiri	Phyllanthaceae	Leaf
200	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	Usiri	Phyllanthaceae	Fruit
201	<i>Physalis angulata</i> L.	Budama	Solanaceae	Whole plant
202	<i>Piper longum</i> L.	Pippali	Piperaceae	Fruit
203	<i>Pistia stratiotes</i> L.	Anthara thamara	Araceae	Leaf
204	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	Chitramulamu	Plumbaginaceae	Root
205	<i>Polygala arvensis</i> Willd.	Nelajanumu	Polygalaceae	Leaf
206	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	Kanuga	Fabaceae	Seed
207	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce	Jammi	Fabaceae	Stem bark
208	<i>Pseudarthria viscida</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	Nayakuponna	Fabaceae	Root
209	<i>Psidium guajava</i> L.	Jama	Myrtaceae	Leaf
210	<i>Pterocarpus marsupium</i> Roxb.	Yegisa	Fabaceae	Stem bark
211	<i>Pterocarpus santalinus</i> L.f.	Errachandanam	Fabaceae	Stem bark
212	<i>Pueraria tuberosa</i> (Willd.) DC.	Nela gummadi	Fabaceae	Tuber
213	<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	Danimma	Punicaceae	Fruit
214	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Benth. ex Kurz	Sarpagandhi	Apocynaceae	Root, leaf
215	<i>Ricinus communis</i> L.	Amudam	Euphorbiaceae	Seed
216	<i>Rivea hypocrateriformis</i> Choisy	Boddikura	Convolvulaceae	Root
217	<i>Sansevieria roxburghiana</i> Schult. & Schult.f.	Chaarala kalabanda	Agavaceae	Leaf
218	<i>Santalum album</i> L.	Gandham	Santalaceae	Stem
219	<i>Sapindus emarginatus</i> Vahl	Kunkudu	Sapindaceae	Fruit
220	<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Konda pala	Apocynaceae	Latex
221	<i>Sauropus androgynus</i> (L.) Merr.	Multivitamin	Phyllanthaceae	Leaf
222	<i>Schleichera oleosa</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Pusuku	Sapindaceae	Stem bark

223	<i>Scoparia dulcis</i> L.	Goda tulsi	Scrophulariaceae	Leaf
224	<i>Semecarpus anacardium</i> L.f.	Nallajeedi	Anacardiaceae	Resin, seed
225	<i>Senna alata</i> (L.) Roxb.	Thamara chettu	Fabaceae	Leaf
226	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	Penta chennangi	Fabaceae	Leaf, whole plant
227	<i>Senna tora</i> (L.) Roxb.	Thagarisa	Fabaceae	Leaf
228	<i>Sesamum indicum</i> L.	Nuvvulu	Pedaliaceae	Leaf
229	<i>Sesbania grandiflora</i> (L.) Pers.	Avise	Fabaceae	Root, stem bark
230	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	Chiluka parre	Malvaceae	Whole plant
231	<i>Sida cordata</i> (Burm.f.) Borss. Waalk.	Gayapaku	Malvaceae	Leaf
232	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	Chiru benda	Malvaceae	Root
233	<i>Sida rhombifolia</i> L.	Athibala	Malvaceae	Leaf
234	<i>Smilax zeylanica</i> L.	Firangi mokka	Smilacaceae	Root
235	<i>Solanum americanum</i> Mill.	Kaachi	Solanaceae	Fruit
236	<i>Solanum toroum</i> Sw.	Konda vanga	Solanaceae	Fruit
237	<i>Solanum trilobatum</i> L.	Mulla vanga	Solanaceae	Leaf
238	<i>Solanum virginianum</i> L.	Nela mulakkaya	Solanaceae	Fruit
239	<i>Solena amplexicaulis</i> (Lam.) Gandhi	Adavi donda	Cucurbitaceae	Root
240	<i>Soymida febrifuga</i> (Roxb.) A.Juss.	Somidi	Meliaceae	Seed
241	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	Bodasaram	Asteraceae	Whole plant
242	<i>Stachytarpheta jamaicensis</i> (L.) Vahl	Kada uttareni	Verbenaceae	Root
243	<i>Stemona tuberosa</i> Lour.	Kanepu teega	Stemonaceae	Tuber
244	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.	Vishamushti	Loganiaceae	Fruit, seed
245	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i> L.f.	Chilla	Loganiaceae	Leaf, fruit, resin
246	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.) Skeels	Neredu	Myrtaceae	Fruit
247	<i>Tabernaemontana divaricata</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Roem. & Shult.	Chakrapu puvvulu	Apocynaceae	Flower
248	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L.	Chinta	Fabaceae	Leaf, fruit
249	<i>Tectona grandis</i> L.	Teku	Lamiaceae	Wood
250	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.) Pers.	Vempali	Fabaceae	Root, leaf
251	<i>Teramnus labialis</i> (L.f.) Spreng.	Adavi minumulu	Fabaceae	Whole plant
252	<i>Terminalia alata</i> Roth	Nallamaddi	Combretaceae	Stem bark
253	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wight & Arn.	Tellamaddi	Combretaceae	Stem bark
254	<i>Terminalia bellirica</i> (Gaertn.) Roxb.	Thaani	Combretaceae	Fruit
255	<i>Terminalia chebula</i> Retz.	Karakkaya	Combretaceae	Fruit
256	<i>Thespesia lampas</i> (Cav.) Dalz.	Adavi patti	Malvaceae	Seed
257	<i>Tinospora cordifolia</i> (Lour.) Merr.	Tippa teega	Menispermaceae	Leaf
258	<i>Toddalia asiatica</i> (L.) Lam.	Konda kasinda	Rutaceae	Fruit
259	<i>Tragia involucreta</i> L.	Dulagondi	Euphorbiaceae	Leaf
260	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L. (f. flava)	Tellagalijeru	Aizoaceae	Leaf
261	<i>Tribulus lanuginosus</i> L.	Palleru	Zygophyllaceae	Leaf
262	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) Lehm.	Nela nakshatralu	Boraginaceae	Leaf
263	<i>Trichosanthes cucumerina</i> L.	Adavi potla	Cucurbitaceae	Fruit
264	<i>Trichuriella monsoniae</i> (L.f.) Bennet	Yerra pindi	Amaranthaceae	Whole plant
265	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> L.	Nallalam	Asteraceae	Leaf
266	<i>Trigonella foenum-graecum</i> L.	Menthulu	Apiaceae	Seed
267	<i>Tylophora indica</i> (Burm.f.) Merr.	Mekameyani aku	Apocynaceae	Root, leaf

268	<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	Nallabenda	Malvaceae	Leaf
269	<i>Vanda tessellata</i> (Roxb.) Hook. ex G.Don	Vadanika	Orchidaceae	Leaf
270	<i>Ventilago maderaspatana</i> Gaertn.	Surla teega	Rhamnaceae	Stem bark
271	<i>Vitex negundo</i> L.	Vavili	Lamiaceae	Leaf
272	<i>Waltheria indica</i> L.	Dubbadulicheru	Malvaceae	Leaf
273	<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L.) Dunal	Dommadolu gadda	Solanaceae	Tuber
274	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> (Roxb.) R.Br.	Palavareni	Apocynaceae	Leaf
275	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	Marula mathangi	Asteraceae	Leaf
276	<i>Xylia xylocarpa</i> (Roxb.) Taub.	Bojja	Fabaceae	Stem bark
277	<i>Zingiber officinale</i> Roscoe	Allam	Zingiberaceae	Rhizome
278	<i>Ziziphus oenopolia</i> (L.) Mill.	Pariki	Rhamnaceae	Leaf
279	<i>Ziziphus rugosa</i> Lam.	Enugu pariki	Rhamnaceae	Leaf
280	<i>Ziziphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Willd.	Gotte	Rhamnaceae	Stem bark